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3 **Suppression of prolactin and reduction of milk secretion by effect of**
4 **cabergoline in lactating dairy ewes**

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ABSTRACT

10 The effects of cabergoline, an ergot derivative and dopamine receptors agonist, were
11 investigated in 30 ewes of 2 dairy breeds (Manchega, MN, n = 15; Lacaune, LC, n = 15).
12 Ewes were in similar late-lactation stage, but differed in milk yield according to breed (MN
13 vs. LC, 1.02 ± 0.03 vs. 2.27 ± 0.05 kg/d). Treatments consisted of a single i.m. injection of
14 cabergoline (Velactis, 1.12 mg/mL cabergoline; Ceva, Libourne, FR) at different doses per
15 ewe: L (low, 0.56 mg) H (high, 1.12 mg) and CO (control, 1 mL saline). Milk yield was
16 recorded daily (d -14 to 25), milk and blood sampled, and udder traits measured from d -2 to
17 14 after injection. No local reaction in the injection site, as well as on behavior and metabolic
18 indicators of the ewes were detected after the cabergoline injection, but milk yield fell rapidly
19 in both breeds (MN vs. LC, -54% vs. -27%), when compared to CO ewes. Cabergoline
20 effects progressively disappeared after d 5 and no milk yield differences between treatments
21 were detected from d 8 to 25 after injection. Milk fat and protein contents increased similarly
22 (22% and 23%; respectively) in both breeds and at both cabergoline doses until d 5, whereas
23 milk lactose tended to decrease (-8%); the effects disappeared thereafter. Plasma prolactin
24 (PRL) decreased dramatically in the L and H treated ewes the day after injection, when

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25 compared to the CO ewes, and reached values below the detection limit of the assay between
26 d 1 and 5, increasing similarly thereafter. On d 14, PRL values were 58% greater in the L and
27 H treated than in the CO ewes, showing that PRL concentrations rebounded when the
28 cabergoline effects ceased. Total udder volume positively correlated with milk accumulated
29 ($r^2= 0.59$) in all groups of ewes throughout the experiment, suggesting its use as a non-
30 invasive method for the estimation of milk stored in the udder. Udder volume was similar for
31 the L and H ewes, but both values were lower than those of the CO ewes from d 1 to 14 after
32 injection. No other effects on udder size were detected. In conclusion, cabergoline
33 dramatically inhibited PRL secretion and decreased milk yield and udder volume of lactating
34 dairy ewes. The L (0.56 mg/ewe) dose of cabergoline was as effective as the H (1.12 mg/ewe)
35 in the 2 breeds of dairy ewes. These results suggest the interest of cabergoline to facilitate the
36 decrease of milk production in dairy ewes (e.g., dry-off, illness care), although further
37 research in pregnant dairy ewes and during the following lactation is still needed.

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39 **Key words:** ergotic, dairy sheep, milk secretion, prolactin, udder.

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INTRODUCTION

42 Late pregnancy and drying-off are challenging periods for dairy ruminants. Pregnant ewes
43 are susceptible to ketone bodies toxemia and new intramammary infections (IMI) because of
44 the increase of glucose demand and the decrease of immunocompetence (Shwimmer et al.,
45 2008; Fthenakis et al., 2012; Zhao et al., 2019). The risks are greater in high-yielding and
46 twin-bearing ewes (Oddy and Holst, 1991; Silva-del-Río et al., 2010), especially when using
47 low energy diets or feed restriction during drying-off (Caldeira et al., 2007). Additionally,
48 nutrient restriction at dry-off decreases 30% basal blood prolactin (PRL) as reported by Ollier
49 et al. (2013) in dairy cows fed hay on the days preceding the dry-off.

50 Dry-off decreases the proliferation of mononuclear cells and compromises
51 immunocompetence (Ollier et al., 2014, 2015; Zhao et al., 2019). Cessation of milking results
52 in udder engorgement which leads to, mammary gland epithelium apoptosis, and if excessive,
53 induces mammary inflammation and cell necrosis (Zobel et al., 2015). In dairy sheep, where
54 abrupt drying-off is commonly done, selective (i.e., IMI positive) or generalized antibiotic
55 therapy is recommended at drying-off to improve udder health and milk yield in the following
56 lactation (Gonzalo et al., 2004; Linage and Gonzalo, 2008). Consequently, reduction of udder
57 insults during dry-off may be a strategy to decrease the use of antibiotic therapies at drying-
58 off.

59 Under a physiological approach, an interesting method to facilitate the dry-off could be
60 inducing the cessation of milk production by interfering with the transmission of hormonal
61 signals from the pituitary gland (i.e., PRL inhibition). This approach has been proposed as a
62 management tool in dairy husbandry (Lacasse et al., 2019) to avoid inappropriate lactation or
63 to alleviate the nutritional stress in sick or injured lactating animals unable to support their
64 level of production.

65 Dopamine has a direct effect on the lactotrophs of the anterior pituitary by binding to their
66 D₂ receptors and reducing PRL exocytosis and gene expression (Fitzgerald and Dinan, 2008).
67 Ergotic (e.g., bromocriptine, cabergoline and metergoline) and non-ergotic (e.g., quinagolide)
68 derivatives also bind to D₂ receptors of the lactotrophs, and have shown to decrease PRL
69 secretion and milk production, although with differences in affinity, half-life and side-effects
70 (Bole-Feysot et al., 1998; Barlier and Jaquet 2006; Kvernmo et al., 2006). The use of PRL
71 inhibitors in lactating ruminants have been deeply reviewed by Lacasse et al. (2012, 2016,
72 2019) and Zhao et al. (2019).

73 Quinagolide has been proved to reduce plasmatic PRL and to be effective for milk
74 reduction, both in early- (Lacasse et al., 2011; Boutinaud et al., 2012) and late-lactating

75 (Ollier et al., 2013, 2014, 2015) dairy cows. Moreover, proliferation and survival of
76 mammary epithelial cells after quinagolide treatment were fully restored by PRL injection
77 (Lollivier et al., 2015; Lacasse et al., 2016), supporting the galactopoietic role of PRL in
78 ruminants.

79 Cabergoline is a highly specific agonist of D₂ receptors with a long elimination half-life
80 (Kvernmo et al., 2006; Odaka et al., 2014). The use of cabergoline, initially authorized by the
81 European Medicines Agency (EMA, 2015) for facilitating the dry-off of cattle, decreased
82 plasma PRL and accelerated udder involution, reducing the secretory activity of mammary
83 epithelial cells, udder engorgement and incidence of milk leakage in dairy cows (Bach et al.,
84 2015; Boutinaud et al., 2016). A large-scale clinical study with 900 dairy cows in 63 farms
85 (Hop et al., 2019), reported that cabergoline decreases under practical conditions the risks of
86 milk leakage and of new IMI during the drying-off and post-calving periods. Nevertheless,
87 despite the positive effects of cabergoline and the no food safety risks for consumers, when
88 withdrawal period is respected (i.e., 32 d during dry-off or 8 milkings during lactation; EMA,
89 2015), its use in high-yielding dairy cows at late pregnancy has been associated to occasional
90 adverse events, usually in the 24-h post-injection. These were recumbency and mortality,
91 which were related to metabolic disorders (i.e., hypocalcemia, hypothermia, ataxia, adipsia,
92 circulatory disorder and diarrhea). Therefore, the marketing authorization of cabergoline as
93 Velactis (Ceva Animal Health, Libourne, FR) was first suspended (EMA, 2016) and finally its
94 use banned in Europe (EMA, 2019), considering that the overall benefit-risk balance in dairy
95 cows was negative.

96 Few and controversial data are available on the use of dopamine agonists in small
97 ruminants. Arlt et al. (2011) reported the inefficacy of cabergoline to cease inappropriate
98 lactations in hobby goats. On the other hand, Lacasse et al. (2016) cited no effects on milk
99 production of repeated injections of quinagolide (1 mg/d for 4 wk; B. Ponchon, V. Lollivier

100 and M. Boutinaud, unpublished results), whereas a single cabergoline injection (1 mg; V.
101 Lollivier and M. Boutinaud, unpublished results) decreases milk yield (–28%) in dairy goats.
102 The effects of dopamine agonists and the adequate dose for dairy ewes are unknown.

103 The objective of this work is to study the effects of 2 doses of cabergoline on PRL
104 suppression and milk secretion to determine the suitable dose and the time-lasting effects in 2
105 breeds of dairy ewes in late-lactation.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

108 The study was conducted in the experimental farm of the SGCE (Servei de Granges i
109 Camps Experimentals) of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB), in Bellaterra
110 (Barcelona, Spain) during 2016. Animal-care conditions and management practices agreed
111 with the Spanish Royal Decree 53/2013 on the protection of animals used for experimental
112 purposes, the codes of recommendations for the welfare of dairy sheep of the Ministry of
113 Agriculture, Alimentation and Environment of Spain (MAPA, 2007) and the procedures
114 stated by the Ethical Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the UAB
115 (Procedure #4992).

116

Ewe Management and Feeding

117 A total of 30 ewes of 2 dairy breeds (MN, Manchega, n = 15; LC, Lacaune, n = 15) in late-
118 lactation (185 ± 11 and 186 ± 11 DIM, respectively; values are means \pm SE) and kept as a
119 single group on wood-chip bedded pens, were used. Their main characteristics (MN and LC,
120 respectively) were: age (3.8 ± 0.5 and 2.7 ± 0.4 yr), BW (73.6 ± 2.5 and 67.6 ± 1.9 kg), BCS
121 (3.08 ± 0.07 and 2.85 ± 0.07), and milk yield (1.02 ± 0.03 and 2.27 ± 0.05 kg/d). All ewes
122 wore ruminal mini-boluses for electronic identification (20 g; Datamars, Bedano, SW) that
123 were used for automatic milk recording (Ait-Said et al., 2014). Machine milking was
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125 conducted twice daily (0700 and 1700) in a 2×12 parallel stall milking parlor with automatic
126 milk-recording devices (MM25SG; DeLaval, Tumba, SE) with similar procedures to those
127 described by Elhadi et al. (2019).

128 Diet consisted of a TMR ad libitum (forage:concentrate, 55:45%; DM basis) with alfalfa
129 hay as forage and a farm-produced concentrate [ingredients: soybean hulls, 50.0%; barley
130 grain, 10.0%; oats grain, 10.0%; gluten feed meal, 10.0%; rapeseed 00 meal, 5.0%; soybean
131 oil, 5.0%; corn grain, 4.0%; bi-calcium phosphate, 2.5%; cane molasses, 2.0%; VitafacOvino-
132 0.3 premix (DSM Nutritional Products, Madrid, ES), 1.0%; salt, 0.5%; as fed]. Additionally,
133 all ewes received 100 g of corn whole grain in the individual feeders of the milking parlor at
134 each milking to encourage their coming in. Nutrient requirements were calculated by
135 INRAtion v.4.07 (Educagri éditions, Dijon, FR). Ewes had free access to water and
136 commercial mineral blocks (Multi-Block; Agrària Comarcal del Vallès, Llerona, ES) in the
137 pens.

138

139 *Experimental Treatments*

140 Ewes were blocked in 3 balanced groups of 10 animals (5 of each breed) according to age,
141 BW, BCS, and milk yield, and submitted to a short-term lactation experiment divided in 2
142 periods: pre- (d -14 to -1) and post-injection (d 0 to 25). The experimental design consisted
143 of a 2×3 factorial (breed×treatment) to which the ewe groups were randomly allocated.
144 Treatments consisted of the dose of cabergoline (Velactis 1.12 mg/mL of cabergoline; Ceva
145 Animal Health) intramuscularly injected into the middle of the left side of the neck after the
146 evening milking, and were: low (0.56 mg of cabergoline/ewe), high (1.12 mg of
147 cabergoline/ewe), and control (CON, 1 mL of saline/ewe). The cabergoline doses used were
148 achieved by the injection of 0.5 or 1.0 mL of Velactis per ewe, close to the EMA (2015)
149 recommended treatment dose (RTD = 5.6 mg/cow or 7 to 10 µg/kg BW), equivalent to 0.49 to

150 0.70 mg of cabergoline for a standard ewe of 70 kg BW, and far from the 3×RTD (1.47 to
151 2.10 mg/ewe) and 5×RTD (2.45 to 3.50 mg/ewe) overdoses injected for the target animal
152 safety studies (EMA, 2015). Collected milk was discarded during the following week
153 according to the withdrawal recommendations.

154

155 *Measurements, Sampling, and Analyses*

156 ***Reactions to the Injection.*** Local tolerance to cabergoline was evaluated on d 0, 1 and 7
157 post-injection using a severity score (0 to 3 points), according to the diameter of the adverse
158 reaction produced by the injection (0, none; 1, <2 cm; 2, between 2 and 8 cm; 3, >8 cm;
159 accuracy, 0.5 points). Special surveillance of the treated ewes was done at 8-h interval by a
160 technician supervised by the veterinarian responsible of the SGCE of the UAB during the 48-
161 h post-injection. General appearance, eating and drinking behavior and mobility of the ewes
162 when attending the twice-daily milking were monitored throughout the experiment.

163 ***Milk Yield.*** Milk yield of individual ewes was recorded by weight at each milking during
164 the whole experimental period (d -14 to 25), using the milk-flow and milk-recording
165 automatic units of the milking parlor (MM25SG, DeLaval). Data were uploaded using the
166 AlPro software 7.2 (DeLaval) and daily reviewed to avoid incorrect values.

167 ***Milk Composition.*** Representative milk samples of each ewe were taken pre- (d -2 and
168 -1) and post- (d 1, 2, 5, 7 and 14) cabergoline injection for compositional analysis using
169 proportional milk samplers (DeLaval). Milk samples (50 mL) were composited according to
170 the daily milking intervals (a.m.:p.m., 60:40), preserved with an antimicrobial tablet
171 (Bronopol; Broad Spectrum Micro-tabs II, D&F Control Systems, San Ramon, CA) and
172 stored at 4°C until analysis. Milk samples were analyzed in the Dairy Herd Improvement
173 Laboratory of Catalonia (ALLIC, Cabrils, ES) for fat, total protein, lactose and urea
174 (Milkoscan FT2; Foss, Hillerød, DK) and SCC (Fossomatic 5000, Foss).

175 **Udder Size.** Udder measurements were recorded before the p.m. milking on d -2 and -1,
176 pre-treatment, and d 2, 5, 7 and 14 post-treatment, according to the agreed-upon FAO-M4
177 study protocol for dairy sheep (Labussière, 1983) with the ewes restrained by head-lockers in
178 the milking stalls. Udder volume was estimated by water displacement using a 5-L bucket of
179 warm water. Udder width was measured as the maximum udder width value by using a
180 surgical thickness compass (Hauptner, Solingen, DE) and udder base-floor distance was taken
181 by a measuring flexible tape, both from the back of the ewes.

182 **Blood Measurements.** Blood samples were taken from the jugular vein using 4-mL
183 Vacutainer tubes with EDTA K2E 7.2 mg (BD; Belliver Industrial Estate, Plymouth, UK) 1-h
184 after the a.m. milking (without corn supplement) and before feeding at d -1 (pre-treatment),
185 and d 1, 2, 5, 7 and 14 (post-treatment). EDTA blood collecting tubes were used to avoid
186 possible interactions in the hormonal enzymatic competitive analyses (Kohék et al., 2002).
187 Plasma was obtained by blood centrifugation for 15 min at $2,000 \times g$ and 4°C , transferred to
188 0.5 mL Eppendorf tubes and stored at -20°C for analysis.

189 Concentration of PRL in plasma was measured by ELISA sandwich type analysis (human
190 PRL-ELISA KAPD1291, DIAsource Immunoassays, Leuven, BE) and the stopped ELISA
191 plates were read in an automatic reader (iEMS Reader MF V.2.9-0; Labsystems España,
192 Barcelona, ES) at 450 nm. Detection limit, intra and inter assay CV were 0.35 ng/mL, 5.5 and
193 6.5%, respectively.

194 Impact of cabergoline treatments on the metabolic status of the ewes was assessed by the
195 plasmatic concentrations of glucose, lactate, γ -glutamyl transferase (GGT), phosphorus and
196 creatinine, using an Olympus AU480 analyzer (Olympus Europa, Hamburg, DE) with the
197 specific Reagent System of Olympus (OSR, Beckman Coulter, Krefeld, IE); the respective
198 analytical methods and reagents used were: hexokinase method (OSR6121), lactate oxidase
199 method (OSR6193), γ -glutamyl-3-carboxy-4-nitroanilide method (OSR6119, with a

200 concentration greater than 4 mmol/L), phospho molybdate method (OSR6122) and the Jaffé
201 method (OSR6178). Changes in absorbance were read at 340 nm, except for creatinine that
202 were read at 520 nm. Non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA) were determined by enzymatic
203 colorimetry (ACS-ACOD-MEHA; acyl-CoA synthetase, acyl-CoA oxidase, 3-methyl-N-
204 ethyl-N(β -hydroxy-ethyl) aniline) in the same analyzer using NEFA HR reagents (Fujifilm
205 Wako Chemicals, Neuss, DE) and read at 410 nm. Additionally, concentration of lactose in
206 plasma was used as indicator of the leakiness of the lactocyte tight junctions and was
207 analyzed by difference based on two enzymatic reactions using galactose dehydrogenase and
208 β -galactosidase, one measuring galactose and the other lactose and galactose (Boehringer
209 Mannheim/R-Biopharm, Darmstad, DE) in the Olympus AU480 analyzer and reading at 340
210 nm. The use of EDTA collecting tubes did not allow the analyses of Ca, K and Na in plasma.

211

212 *Statistical Analyses*

213 Data were analyzed by the MIXED procedure for repeated measurements of SAS v.9.4
214 (SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC). The statistical mixed model to evaluate the similarity of the
215 ewe's groups during the pre-treatment period and the response to the treatments contained the
216 fixed effects of breed (MN and LC), cabergoline dose (L, H and CO), sampling time and
217 breed \times treatment interaction, as well as the random effects of the experimental unit (the
218 animal), and the residual error. Values of the variables were computed for their respective
219 treatment and sampling dates, the means expressed as least squares means (LSM) and
220 separated by pairwise comparison using the PDIFF ADJUST=SCHEFFE test of SAS. Pearson
221 correlation (r) coefficients were calculated using the CORR procedure of SAS. Significance
222 was declared at $P < 0.05$ and a tendency was considered when $P < 0.10$.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

225 ***Cabergoline Dosage.*** According to the mean BW of the dairy ewes enrolled in the
226 experiment (MN and LC, 73.6 and 67.6 kg BW, on average, respectively), the chosen
227 cabergoline doses (L and H, respectively) were slightly lower in the MN (7.6 and 15.2 µg/kg
228 BW) than in the LC (8.3 and 16.6 µg/kg BW) ewes. The L dose fell in the range of the EMA
229 (2015) recommended treatment dose of cabergoline (RTD = 7 to 10 µg/kg BW) and agreed
230 with the dosage previously used for the dry-off of dairy cows (Boutinaud et al., 2016; 8.7
231 µg/kg BW). On the other hand, the H dose doubled the RTD but was far from the 3×RTD (21
232 to 30 µg/kg BW) and 5×RTD (35 to 50 µg/kg BW) overdoses injected for target animal safety
233 studies (EMA, 2015). As previously indicated by Lacasse et al. (2016, 2019), and despite the
234 inconsistency of some studies done in goats, a dose of 1.0 mg cabergoline (approximately
235 16.6 µg/kg BW for a 60 kg BW goat) was also used in high-yielding dairy goats (i.e., 3.5 kg/d
236 milk) in early-lactation. Interestingly, this high dose would have the advantage of increasing
237 the possible side and adverse effects of cabergoline in small ruminants.

238 ***Reaction to Cabergoline Injection.*** Intramuscular injection of cabergoline at both L and H
239 doses did not produce local or adverse reactions in the right site of the ewes' neck; only 3 MN
240 ewes, 1 from each treatment (i.e., CO, L and H), showed a slight swelling reaction (score 1) to
241 the injection. No swelling reactions were observed in the LC ewes characterized by having
242 open fleeces and wool-uncovered necks compared to MN, which may have allowed a more
243 precise and clean i.m. injection. As a consequence, the values of swelling scores were very
244 low and similar between treatments (0.10 ± 0.11 , on average).

245 Regardless of the cabergoline dose used, no general reactions or apparent changes in the
246 behavior of the L and H treated ewes (i.e., abatement, recumbency, lack of interest to the feed
247 bunk or drinkers after feed offering), were detected during the 48-h post-injection and
248 throughout the experiment, when compared to the CO ewes. Moreover, no changes in the
249 motion of the ewes, when being moved to the twice-daily milking or in their eating behavior

250 in the milking parlor (i.e., refusal of corn whole grain) were recorded. Unfortunately, no data
251 on local or adverse side-effects of the high dose of cabergoline used in the goat experiments
252 were available for comparison (Lacasse et al., 2016, 2019).

253 ***Prolactin in Plasma.*** As shown in Figure 1, plasma concentrations of PRL in the CO ewes
254 ranged between 12 and 24 ng/mL (17.8 ± 1.5 ng/mL, on average) from d -1 to 14; no
255 differences were detected in both breeds ($P = 0.99$). On the contrary, concentrations of PRL
256 dramatically fell in the cabergoline treated ewes (Figure 1) for which values were under the
257 detection limit (i.e. 0.35 ng/mL) during d 1 and 2 post-injection, slightly increased on d 5, and
258 raised rapidly thereafter. The low PRL values persisted for both L and H doses from d 1 to 5
259 when compared to CO ewes (-86%, on average; $P < 0.001$; Table 1), with no differences
260 between breeds ($P = 0.89$; Table 1) and raised after d 7 (Figure 1). Values of plasmatic PRL
261 of our CO ewes 1-h after milking agreed with the basal values reported by Boutinaud et al.
262 (2016) in Holstein dairy cows before milking (approximately, 16 ng/mL). Nevertheless, the
263 effect of cabergoline injection on the PRL concentration of our lactating ewes was greater
264 than the decrease reported by Boutinaud et al. (2016; -39%) in Holstein dairy cows at dry-off,
265 when compared to conventionally dried cows and both fed a dry hay diet. This lower PRL
266 difference may have been a consequence of the negative effect of feed restriction in the
267 control cows, as previously reported by Ollier et al. (2013). Additionally, the difference
268 between control and cabergoline injected cows in the Boutinaud et al (2016) study, persisted
269 for 8-d and disappeared on d 14, likewise as it was observed in our ewes (Figure 1).
270 Moreover, -20% plasma PRL after cabergoline injection was reported in the Bach et al.
271 (2015) study, but the authors did not mention the cow's BW and the blood sampling time with
272 regard to milking, precluding the comparison with other data.

273 Lacasse et al. (2011) and Boutinaud et al. (2012) also reported decreases in the
274 concentrations of PRL released at milking (-12 to -32%) in dairy cows treated with repeated
275 injections of quinagolide during lactation (8-wk).

276 Interestingly, greater PRL values in plasma were detected on d 14 post-injection in the L
277 and H ewes (58%, on average; $P < 0.001$), when compared to the CO ewes, indicating a PRL
278 rebound effect after ceasing the cabergoline treatment (Figure 1). The PRL rebound was the
279 response (paradoxical reaction) of the ewe's metabolism to return to its basal state
280 (homeostasis) after having been modified by the injection of cabergoline. Evidence of PRL
281 rebound can also be observed in the results of Ollier et al. (2013) in dairy cows injected with
282 quinagolide for 4-d before dry-off (approximately 50% increase basal value at d 14 post-
283 injection), but it was not visible in the Bach et al. (2015) and Boutinaud et al. (2016) dairy
284 cows injected with cabergoline at dry-off.

285 Given that cabergoline half-life in cows is 19-h (EMA, 2015) and its high affinity for
286 dopamine D₂-like receptors (Kvernmo et al., 2006), the occurrence of the PRL rebound on d
287 14 after injection may be related to a mid-term feed-back of pituitary's lactotrophs, decreasing
288 the release of natural dopamine, which will result in a rise of PRL. Mechanism of PRL
289 rebound in rats after dopamine withdrawal was explained by Chen et al. (1993) and Chang
290 and Shin (1999), who demonstrated that dopamine acts on D₂ receptors both to inhibit and to
291 stimulate PRL release. We hypothesize that this may be related to the decrease of the activity
292 of tyrosine hydroxylase (TH), the rate-limiting key enzyme in the biosynthesis and
293 availability of catecholamines (i.e., dopamine, noradrenaline and adrenaline) during the
294 cabergoline treatment. Gordon et al. (2008) showed that TH binds to dopamine in high- and
295 low-affinity binding sites, and dissociation of TH from dopamine markedly increases TH
296 activity that will lead to greater PRL concentration in blood.

297 **Milk Yield.** All of the ewes were healthy at the start of the experiment and showed high
298 milk yields for late-lactation before applying the treatments (Figure 2). Lactation persistency,
299 estimated as the linear slope of the milk yield curve according to the stage of lactation was –
300 18 g/d for the CO ewes ($y = -0.0178x + 1.44$; $r^2 = 0.85$, $P < 0.001$) during the whole
301 experiment (d –14 to 25), with differences in both breeds. Persistency was inverse to the level
302 of production of each breed (MN, –6 g/d; LC, –28 g/d; $P = 0.004$), the lower the yield, the
303 higher the persistency.

304 Milk yield fell rapidly during the first 5 d after treatment (Figure 2 and Table 1) for both
305 cabergoline doses (L vs. H, –40% vs. –22%; $P < 0.001$) and ewe breeds (MN and LC, –54%
306 and –27%; $P < 0.001$), when compared to CO ewes. On average, the injection of cabergoline
307 produced a sudden and marked decrease of milk yield (–31%; $P < 0.001$) immediately after
308 the treatment and the slope (d 1 to 5) of the milk regression was –64 g/d of milk, on average.
309 Milk yield progressively recovered after d 5, and no differences were detected between the
310 CO and the cabergoline treated ewes on d 8 after injection ($P = 0.23$) and thereafter (d 9 to 25;
311 $P = 0.49$). Nevertheless, all ewes showed an unexpected increase in milk yield between d 8 to
312 10 (26%, on average), followed by a milk drop on d 11 and 12 (–20%, on average; Figure 2),
313 without differences between the CO and the cabergoline treated ewes ($P = 0.90$). As a result,
314 the persistency of the cabergoline treated ewes throughout the whole experiment (d –14 to 25)
315 was on average –23 g/d ($y = -0.0233x + 1.35$; $r^2 = 0.72$, $P < 0.001$), similar to the CO ewes (P
316 = 0.35) and without differences between the H and L doses ($P = 0.85$). Again, persistency was
317 inverse to the yield of each breed (MN, –16 g/d; LC, –30 g/d; $P = 0.026$).

318 Milk yield also declines faster in quinagolide treated cows (daily injections for 8-wk)
319 during lactation than in control cows (Lacasse et al., 2011; approximately –15%), but no
320 effects of a single injection of cabergoline have been tested during lactation. Milk decrease
321 after the cabergoline injection in our ewes duplicated the above indicated value in dairy cows.

322 The increase in milk yield after d 11 was unlikely produced by the PRL rebound because
323 the parallel raise in milk yield of the CO ewes and the numerically greater concentration of
324 PRL in the plasma of the L treated ewes (Figure 1).

325 **Milk Composition.** On average, milk fat (Figure 3a) and milk protein (Figure 3b) contents
326 of our ewes increased rapidly from d 1 to 5 (22 and 23%, respectively; $P < 0.001$) after the
327 cabergoline treatment. Despite these increases in milk component concentrations, daily yields
328 of milk fat and milk protein tended to decrease ($P = 0.07$ and $P = 0.10$, respectively; Table 1)
329 as a result of the decrease in milk yield produced by the cabergoline injection. The effects on
330 milk fat and protein contents disappeared after d 7 post-injection, accompanying the recovery
331 of milk yield previously discussed after d 5. On the contrary, lactose content in milk only
332 decreased numerically (-8% ; $P < 0.11$) suggesting a possible inhibitory effect of cabergoline,
333 although the difference was only significant on d 2 and 5 (Figure 3c) for the H dose ($P =$
334 0.042). The differences in milk composition among treatments decreased after d 7 and no
335 differences in the concentration of milk components were detected thereafter.

336 Despite the reported drop in milk yield of quinagolide treated cows during lactation
337 (Lacasse et al., 2011) only numerically greater milk fat and milk protein contents are found in
338 milk; nevertheless, daily yields of both milk fat and milk protein decrease, agreeing with the
339 results obtained in our ewes. Moreover, marked decreases of milk lactose content during the
340 last 4-wk of treatment and of lactose yield are reported by Lacasse et al. (2011) in the
341 quinagolide treated cows, agreeing with our results in cabergoline treated ewes during
342 lactation. Conversely, Boutinaud et al. (2016) did not find effects on the composition of
343 mammary secretions (i.e., fat, protein and lactose) of Holstein cows treated with cabergoline
344 at dry-off, although the composition of mammary secretions after ceasing milking is not
345 directly comparable to that of milk obtained at milkings during lactation.

346 No effects of cabergoline treatment were detected on the SCC of our ewes ($P = 0.50$; Table
347 1) that, despite being in late-lactation, showed a low SCC (5.40 ± 0.26 , on average, equivalent
348 to 250,000 cells/mL). Ollier et al. (2014, 2015) and Boutinaud et al. (2016) reported a rise in
349 the SCC of dairy cows treated with quinagolide or cabergoline at drying-off, respectively, in
350 comparison to control cows, although the rise disappeared after d 4 (Boutinaud et al., 2016).

351 All effects of cabergoline on milk composition of our ewes disappeared after the first week
352 post-treatment and no differences with the CO ewes were detectable at d 14.

353 **Metabolic Indicators.** Impact of cabergoline treatments on the metabolic status of the ewes
354 was assessed by the plasmatic concentrations of several metabolic indicators during the
355 critical period post-treatment (d 1 to 5), as well as for glucose and creatinine during the whole
356 experiment (data not shown). No effects of cabergoline treatment were detected on glucose,
357 NEFA, lactate and the GGT liver enzyme (related to glutathione metabolism, amino acid
358 absorption and protection against oxidation) as shown in Table 1. Moreover, glucose and
359 creatinine in plasma were steadied throughout the whole experimental period ($P = 0.97$).
360 Plasmatic values of NEFA tended to be greater in the LC ewes, according to their greater milk
361 production ($P = 0.08$; Table 1) but did not differ by cabergoline treatment ($P = 0.89$),
362 indicating that cabergoline did not produce metabolic stress in our ewes. Similar results were
363 obtained by Ollier et al. (2014) in quinagolide treated dairy cows during drying-off.

364 Although it was not possible to analyze Ca and Mg values because of the EDTA collecting
365 blood tubes, no differences in plasmatic P values were detected (4.50 ± 0.31 mg P/dL, on
366 average) between treatments ($P = 0.89$) or breeds ($P = 0.49$). According to Venjakob et al.
367 (2017), there are positive associations between serum Ca and P concentrations in dairy cows,
368 suggesting that no differences in blood Ca would be expected as a result of the cabergoline
369 injection in our ewes. Lacasse et al. (2019) concluded that lowering the PRL concentration by

370 dopamine agonists is unlikely to be responsible of a reduction in blood Ca and to cause
371 hypocalcemia, as it was suspected in the cabergoline banning decision of EMA (2016, 2019).

372 No differences in plasma lactose were detected by effect of the cabergoline treatment in
373 our ewes ($P = 0.84$; Table 1), although marked differences were observed according to breed
374 ($P = 0.048$); the LC having greater values than MN ewes. This result agree with previous data
375 in the same breeds and with the fact that LC ewes have greater milk yield and are more
376 tolerant to milk accumulation between milkings than the MN are (Castillo et al., 2008).
377 Consequently, no tight junction disruption (leakiness) was produced in our ewes despite their
378 level of production, as a result of the injection of cabergoline. Milk lactose reduction in our
379 ewes could be explained by the reduction of lactose synthesis in the mammary epithelial cells
380 and not by leaking trough the cellular tight junctions.

381 **Udder Traits.** Involution of the udder induced by the cabergoline treatment was assessed
382 by the changes in its anatomical measurements. The greater the reduction of the udder size,
383 the better the effectivity of the dry-off facilitation treatment. Udder size will be an objective
384 non-invasive criterion to monitor the involution of the udder during the dry-off. Data of the
385 udder volume (range, 1.00 to 3.42 L) and the corresponding milk yield obtained at the p.m.
386 milking (range, 0.07 to 1.41 kg) of our ewes throughout the experiment (d -2 to 14) positively
387 correlated ($y = 0.4034 x - 0.226$; $r^2 = 0.59$, $P < 0.01$; Figure 4), without differences among
388 treatments. Udder volume differed between breeds in our ewes (MN, 1.57 ± 0.07 ; LC, $2.23 \pm$
389 0.07 ; $P < 0.001$), agreeing with their differences in milk yield. Additionally, the volume of the
390 mammary tissue (non-milk volume of the udder) estimated by difference also correlated with
391 the total volume of the udder ($r = 0.82$, $P < 0.001$). Labussière (1983), in a prospective study
392 on the milkability of different dairy breeds in the Mediterranean, reported positive
393 correlations between udder volume and daily milk yield ($r = 0.40$ to 0.71), although the
394 reported correlations vary with the age of the ewes and the milk fraction considered, as also

395 indicated by Fernández et al. (1983) in Manchega dairy ewes ($r = 0.16$ to 0.85). Similarly,
396 udder width (MN, 12.6 ± 0.3 ; LC, 14.8 ± 0.3 ; $P < 0.001$) and base-floor distance (MN, $34.1 \pm$
397 1.1 ; LC, 28.3 ± 1.1 ; $P < 0.001$) also were, on average, different between breeds in our ewes,
398 the greater the yield the greater the size of the udder.

399 With regard to the cabergoline treatments, volume and width of the udder (Figure 5) were
400 similar for the ewes treated with the L and H doses of cabergoline ($P = 0.36$ and $P = 0.56$,
401 respectively) but, on average, udder volume was lower (-18% ; $P < 0.001$) and udder width
402 tended to be lower (-6% ; $P = 0.09$) than those of the CO ewes from d 2 to 5 (Table 1).
403 Nevertheless, no differences in udder volume were detected in the LC ewes ($P = 0.57$).
404 Interestingly, despite not having differences in milk yield between CO and both L and H
405 treatments at d 14 post-injection, udder volume of the cabergoline treated ewes remained
406 smaller than in the CO ewes (Figure 5a). This result may be the consequence of a reduction of
407 the secretory tissue of the udder (i.e., mammary gland involution), which was only
408 observed in the case of the treated MN ewes ($P = 0.045$), but that did not affect milk yield in
409 the late stage of lactation of our ewes. There is also the possibility of a side-effect of the PRL
410 rebound on oxytocin secreted at milking, agreeing with the oxytocin-PRL positive feedback
411 suggested by Kennett and McKee (2012) in rats, which may have reduced the amount of
412 residual milk in the cabergoline-treated ewes. This last hypothesis needs further research. No
413 effects of treatments were detected on the base-floor distance of the udder of either breed of
414 ewes ($P = 0.53$; Table 1), indicating that premilking udder volume and, to a lesser extent, the
415 premilking udder width were the only useful morphological traits to assess udder involution.

416

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CONCLUSIONS

418 Cabergoline temporarily inhibited PRL and markedly decreased milk secretion and udder
419 volume, but increased most milk components in lactating dairy ewes. The effect disappeared

420 after 5 d, and milk yield and milk composition did not differ from CON values when milking
421 was maintained for more than 20 d after injection. The effect on udder volume lasted longer
422 than the effect on milk yield, which may be related to the PRL rebound after cessation of
423 cabergoline treatment, and needs further research. The low dose was as effective as the high
424 dose of cabergoline for the reduction of lactation, without differences between them with
425 regard to udder traits. Overall, the use of 0.56 mg/ewe of cabergoline as a dry-off facilitator
426 may be a strategy of interest in high-yielding dairy ewes to reduce feed-restriction stress (i.e.,
427 ketosis risk) and antibiotic therapy at dry-off. No apparent adverse reactions were detected,
428 and our data do not support the suspicion that use of cabergoline, at the RTD, may be related
429 to hypocalcemia or mammary epithelial cell tight junctions disruption in lactating dairy ewes.
430 Additionally, the results of this study may be useful to understand the use of PRL inhibitors as
431 a management tool in dairy small ruminants. Further research on the use of cabergoline on
432 pregnant dairy ewes at the dry-off and during the following lactation is needed. Finally, it
433 should be stressed that the use of cabergoline is currently suspended in the European Union
434 for cattle, and that its use in dairy sheep will require a specific approval by EMA.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

437 This study was partially and funded by Ceva Animal Health (Libourne, FR). The authors
438 are grateful to Drs Alex Martino and Alessio Valenza, Vets Ana I. de Prado-Taranilla and
439 Juan-Pedro Casas, from Ceva Animal Health for their advice and support. Thanks are also
440 extended to Ramón Costa and the technical team of the SGCE (Servei de Granges i Camps
441 Experimentals) of the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (Bellaterra, Barcelona, ES) for the
442 care of the animals, and to Charles (Chuck) Simmons, native English-speaking former
443 Instructor of English (Cerdanyola, Barcelona, Spain) for the English language and style
444 revision of the manuscript.

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606 **Table 1.** Lactational effects of a single injection of cabergoline at different doses¹ during d 1 to 5 post-injection in two breeds of dairy ewes in
607 late-lactation (data are LS means \pm SEM)

Item	Manchega			Lacaune			Mean	\pm SEM	Effect (<i>P</i> -value)		
	CO	L	H	CO	L	H			Cabergoline	Breed	Interaction ²
Milk yields											
Milk, kg/d	0.87 ^a	0.40 ^b	0.62 ^{ab}	1.84 ^a	1.34 ^b	1.56 ^{ab}	1.11	0.12	0.001	0.001	0.99
ECM ³ , kg/d	1.03 ^a	0.59 ^b	0.88 ^{ab}	1.88	1.55	1.82	1.29	0.13	0.050	0.001	0.95
Fat, g/d	80 ^x	48 ^y	72 ^x	138 ^x	115 ^y	137 ^x	98	11	0.07	0.001	0.93
Protein, g/d	63 ^x	37 ^y	54 ^x	116 ^x	101 ^y	116 ^x	81	8	0.10	0.001	0.97
Lactose, g/d	36 ^a	16 ^b	22 ^{ab}	80 ^a	52 ^b	63 ^{ab}	45	6	0.003	0.001	0.96
Milk contents											
Fat, %	9.15 ^b	11.74 ^a	11.64 ^a	7.49 ^b	8.60 ^a	8.82 ^a	9.57	0.54	0.001	0.001	0.36
Protein, %	7.28 ^b	9.26 ^a	8.63 ^a	6.31 ^b	7.51 ^a	7.44 ^a	7.74	0.41	0.001	0.001	0.63
Lactose, %	4.13	3.87	3.58	4.33	3.90	4.03	3.97	0.16	0.11	0.20	0.60
SCC, log ₁₀ /mL	5.24	5.36	5.36	5.28	5.76	5.42	5.40	0.25	0.50	0.43	0.74
Plasma											
Prolactin, ng/mL	19.34 ^a	0.65 ^b	0.56 ^b	19.21 ^a	1.22 ^b	0.91 ^b	6.98	2.37	0.001	0.89	0.99
Glucose, mg/dL	62	60	60	60	64	59	61	2	0.61	0.81	0.42
NEFA, mmol/dL	0.075	0.083	0.070	0.101	0.088	0.114	0.087	0.011	0.89	0.08	0.16
Lactate, mmol/L	0.93	1.32	1.21	1.02	1.12	0.92	1.04	0.21	0.49	0.43	0.88
GGT ⁴ , IU/L	58	60	47	77	88	67	66	12	0.53	0.12	0.80
P, mg/dL	4.23	4.57	4.28	4.73	4.44	5.03	4.50	0.31	0.89	0.49	0.34
Creatinine, mg/dL	0.68	0.71	0.71	0.64	0.67	0.65	0.68	0.03	0.69	0.08	0.98
Lactose, μ mol/L	10.8	6.8	8.0	35.8	31.9	39.8	21.2	12.3	0.84	0.048	0.97
Udder traits ⁵											
Volume, L	1.96 ^a	1.41 ^b	1.35 ^b	2.36	2.13	2.19	1.90	0.13	0.005	0.001	0.20
Width, cm	13.2	12.3	12.3	15.3 ^x	14.2 ^b	14.8 ^{xy}	13.7	0.5	0.09	0.001	0.83
Base-floor, cm	31.9	34.0	36.4	28.4	31.8	28.5	31.2	1.9	0.53	0.001	0.47

608 ^{a,b}Within a row and breed, values with a different superscript differed ($P < 0.05$); ^{x,y}Within a row and breed, values with a different superscript
609 tended to differ ($P < 0.10$).

610 ¹Treatments: CO, 0 mg; L, 0.56 mg; H, 1.12 mg cabergoline per ewe.

611 ²Cabergoline \times Breed.

612 ³Energy corrected milk = Milk yield \times [0.071 \times (Fat, %) + 0.043 \times (Total protein, %) + 0.2224], according to Bocquier et al. (1993).

613 ⁴ γ -glutamyl transferase.

614 ⁵Data from d 2 to 5 post-injection.

615 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

616 **Figure 1.** Effects of a single injection of cabergoline at different doses on plasma PRL of
617 lactating Manchega and Lacaune dairy ewes. Doses of cabergoline: ▲ (H, 1.12 mg; n = 10), ■
618 (L, 0.56 mg; n = 10), and ○ (CO, 0 mg; n = 10). Values are LS means of both breeds
619 averaged, with the SEM indicated by vertical bars. Differences between control and
620 cabergoline i.m. injected ewes were significant ($P < 0.001$) from d 1 to 7.

621
622 **Figure 2.** Effects of a single injection of cabergoline at different doses on milk yield of
623 lactating Manchega and Lacaune dairy ewes. Doses of cabergoline: ▲ (H, 1.12 mg; n = 10), ■
624 (L, 0.56 mg; n = 10), and ○ (CO, 0 mg; n = 10). Values are LS means of both breeds
625 averaged, with the SEM indicated by vertical bars. Differences between control and
626 cabergoline i.m. injected ewes were significant ($P < 0.001$) from d 1 to 5.

627
628 **Figure 3.** Effects of a single injection of cabergoline at different doses on milk composition
629 (a, fat; b, protein; c, lactose) of lactating Manchega and Lacaune dairy ewes. Doses of
630 cabergoline: ▲ (H, 1.12 mg; n = 10), ■ (L, 0.56 mg; n = 10), and ○ (CO, 0 mg; n = 10).
631 Values are LS means of both breeds averaged, with the SEM indicated by vertical bars.
632 Differences in fat and protein milk contents between control and cabergoline i.m. injected
633 ewes were significant ($P < 0.001$) from d 1 to 5. Lactose milk content tended to decrease ($P <$
634 0.11).

635
636 **Figure 4.** Correlation ($y = 0.4034 x - 0.226$; $r^2 = 0.59$, $P < 0.01$; n = 180) between udder
637 volume and milk yield at p.m. milking of lactating Manchega and Lacaune dairy ewes after a
638 single injection of cabergoline at different doses. Doses of cabergoline: ▲ (H, 1.12 mg; n =
639 60, $r^2 = 0.59$; $P < 0.05$), ■ (L, 0.56 mg; n = 60, $r^2 = 0.68$; $P < 0.05$), and ○ (CO, 0 mg; n = 60,
640 $r^2 = 0.44$; $P < 0.05$).

641
642 **Figure 5.** Effects of a single injection of cabergoline at different doses on the udder traits (a,
643 volume; b, width) of lactating Manchega and Lacaune dairy ewes. Doses of cabergoline: ▲
644 (H, 1.12 mg; n = 10), ■ (L, 0.56 mg; n = 10), and ○ (CO, 0 mg; n = 10). Values are LS means
645 of both breeds averaged, with the SEM indicated by vertical bars. Differences in udder

646 volume between control and cabergoline i.m. injected ewes were significant ($P < 0.001$) from
647 d 2 to 14.
648

649 **Figure 1.**

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654 **Figure 2.**

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658 **Figure 3.**

659 **a)**

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661 **b)**

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663 **c)**

664

665 **Figure 4.**

666

667

668 **Figure 5.**

669 **a)**

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671 **b)**

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